

UTILIZING FLIPGRID, AS A DIGITAL TOOL, IN ASSESSING SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract. *The article emphasize Integrating innovative methods in assessing language ability of learners are critical part of language teaching and learning. The present paper is dedicated to explore integration of digital platform “Flipgrid” where instructor posted tasks and students answer in video format. This innovative tool allowed to process students learning about the content. Students recorded videos were peer and self-assessed with follow-up teacher’s feedback relying on rubric (Grammar and Vocabulary, Discourse Management, Pronunciation, Interactive Communication).*

Keywords: *Impromptu speech, CLT, EFL, types of speaking, interaction, monolog, dialog, polylog, role-playing, simulations*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola o'quvchilarning til qobiliyatini baholashda innovatsion usullardan foydalanish tilni o'qitish va o'rganishning muhim qismiligiga katta urg'u beradi. Ushbu loyiha ishi "Flipgrid" raqamli platformasining integratsiyasini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, u erda o'qituvchi vazifalarni joylashtiradi va talabalar video formatda tarzida javob berishadi. Ushbu innovatsion vosita o'quvchilarni materila mazmunini o'rganishlariga imkon beradi. Talabalar yozib olingan videofilmlar rubrikaga asoslanib tengdoshlari tomonidan va o'zlari tomolaridan baholanadi*

Kalit soʻzlar: *Badiha usuli, CLT, EFL, muloqot turlari, oʻzaro aloqa, monolog, dialog, polelog, rolli oʻyinlar, simulatsiyalar*

In today's digital age, technology plays a pivotal role in transforming various aspects of education, including language assessment. Language assessment, particularly in the domain of language learning and teaching, has seen significant advancements with the integration of technology. This essay delves into the role of technology in language assessment, exploring its benefits, challenges, and implications for language learners and educators.

A mobile software application called Flipgrid (Flipgrid.com) was chosen as an asynchronous platform for conducting speaking activities with students. Flipgrid is a cross-platform application that works on iOS, Android and computer which enables users to make a video recorded “response” which is posted to a thread which Flipgrid calls a “Topic.” Flipgrid was acquired by Microsoft in 2018 and all of its robust offerings of features (video creation tools, unlimited storage, extensive database of free images, etc.) are available for free for teachers as well as students. Flipgrid is by far the most widely used online video creation and sharing platform in the education domain. It has been used in classes of various fields, especially in America. There are also many studies in the literature investigating Flipgrid’s effectiveness in oral skills (Mango, 2019, 2021; Miskam & Saidalvi, 2019; Petersen et al., 2020; Shin & Yunis, 2021). However, literature around the utilization of Flipgrid and its effects on Japanese language students are less common. This paper centers on the efforts to implement Flipgrid in asynchronous courses along with investigation of its efficacy for conducting speaking activities in a communicative-centered EFL course. The positive and negative experiences from students will be presented and examined in this paper too. Accommodating students to have an opportunity in practicing English during the instruction is a crucial matter to reach the communicative objective stated in the curriculum.

Flipgrid appears to have more benefit particularly in teaching and assessing speaking skills. Flipgrid is a free video platform where teachers can create communities by posting discussion prompts that students can generate responses through short video recordings (Difilippantonio-Pen, 2020). Moreover, Flipgrid enables students to customize their video responses as it has rich features, not to mention its user-friendly aspect and secure digital environment between teacher and students (Forsythe & Raine, 2019; Kiles et al., 2020). Several studies on Flipgrid have been conducted where similar results were shown in those studies. Most of the studies that investigated both teachers' and students' perceptions showed a positive attitude toward the use of Flipgrid (Difilippantonio-Pen, 2020; Lim et al., 2021; Petersen et al., 2020; Syahrizal & Pamungkas, 2021; Tuyet & Khang, 2020). Moreover, other studies revealed that Flipgrid improves students' speaking skills, decreases speaking anxiety, and increases students' motivation (Nuridah et al., 2021; Syahrizal & Pamungkas, 2021; Tuyet & Khang, 2020). Speaking Assessment It has been highlighted in the introduction that assessing speaking is another challenge the teachers face during online learning. Particularly in the online teaching model where teachers have limited control over their students, either teaching or assessing speaking at some point seems to be neglected due to its trickiness. Long before a pandemic strikes the world, studies on speaking assessment showed that in the EFL context, students have a negative experience with speaking activities which led to a high level of speaking anxiety (Ariyanti, 2016; Cepik & Yastibas, 2013; Safari & Koosha, 2016; Suleimenova, 2013; Yalçın & İnceçay, 2014). With the current situation that forces teachers to shift the traditional teaching activities into online mode, speaking skills become even harder to be taught due to the existed limitations. However, as has been explained, utilizing Flipgrid as electronic portfolios is applicable to serve both teaching and assessing speaking skills. This pair, by all means, is a bridge that linked the two purposes and still allows teachers to see their students' improvement at the same time. A study conducted by Johnson and Skarphol (2018) claimed that utilizing Flipgrid as an electronic portfolio is recommended to be implemented in online learning. On the other hand, due to the restraint that the teacher faces in online teaching, the assessment should be still conducted purposively. In terms of assessing speaking, teachers might apply a scoring system that fits with the materials being taught. The scoring rubric utilized by Basak (2019) could be applied in assessing speaking as the rubric items are easier to be applied in online assessment. Taking the 5 scales of measurements, the scoring system has 5 aspects that consist of grammatical accuracy and range, vocabulary, content, fluency, and pronunciation. As Flipgrid emerges to be a useful platform in online teaching and electronic portfolio appears to be the powerful tool to cover both teaching and assessment, these two combinations utilize as a promising pair that help teachers in assessing speaking skills during the pandemic outbreak. However, most research studies under this topic only focus the students' perception and its effect on their motivation separately. Not much has been done in investigating the use of Flipgrid as an electronic portfolio assessment. Thus, the implementation of Flipgrid as an electronic portfolio in speaking assessment and the student's perception of the use of the pair is the focus of this research.

Following the university's curriculum, I conducted a lesson on the topic of "Summary writing". Equipping students' with main principles of writing summary, we analyzed weak and strong written summaries being as a group. I created discussion on how to use Reporting Verbs appropriately, while summarizing main ideas of original work. The online educational tool "Flipgrid" was introduced to students and follow up tasks were explained; phrases that are used in giving and receiving compliments were presented

The classroom implemented communicative teaching in language classrooms by incorporating linguistic, sociolinguistic, and pragmatic competences through the use of authentic material.

Linguistic competences involve a set of skills, knowledge, and attitudes that are interrelated and mutually supported in order to conduct a successful scientific communication that may be destined to different communities or audiences (scientific or the general public), who will be able to understand the communicated knowledge and even use it, provided that they have been correctly materialized from a linguistic point of view. However, the basic notion is the competence of an individual in a language. knowing the importance of increasing student linguistic competence, I followed the key principles so students can enhance their knowledge about grammatical patterns like form, meaning and use. By addressing linguistic competence, I was able to conduct effective and engaging class and have an opportunity to develop students' speaking skill with the combination of grammar. I applied "brainstorming" technique to gather students' knowledge on grammatically correct formal and informal phrases do they use while giving and receiving compliments in English language and what Reporting Verbs can be used while summarizing the source material. Then, some correct ways of phrases for complimenting a person's appearance/clothes, performances, possessions in formal and informal were presented. The activities provoked wonder and motivation in learners; moreover, they were able to connect previous knowledge to the school's curriculum and to real world issues. Nevertheless, it was noticed that to design this type of activities could be time demanding, and that constant reflection in language learning theory is required to improve the effectivity of further results.

REFERENCES

1. Alyousef H. S. Teaching Reading Comprehension to ESL.- 2005
2. Beatrice S. Teaching reading in a second Language. 2008.
3. Beaumont M. The Teaching of Reading Skills in s Second Language. 1996.
4. Brindley S. Teaching English. 1994
5. Brown, D. (2001). Teaching by Principles. An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy (Second Edition) New York: Longman.
6. Calhoun E. F. Teaching Beginning Reading and Writing with the picture word inductive model. 1999
7. David L Chiese. Re-conceptualizing language teaching: An in-service teacher Education course in Uzbekistan. 2019
8. Fries Ch «The Structure of English» New York, 1952
9. Hager A. Techniques for Teaching Beginning. 2001